

Supplementary Material for manuscript “Community recommendations for geochemical data, services and analytical capabilities in the 21st century”

M. Klöcking, L. Wyborn, K.A. Lehnert, B. Ware, A.M. Prent, L. Profeta, F. Kohlmann, W. Noble, I. Bruno, S. Lambart, H. Ananuer, N.D. Barber, H. Becker, M. Brodbeck, H. Deng, K. Deng, K. Elger, G. de Souza Franco, Y. Gao, K.M. Ghasera, D.C. Hezel, J. Huang, B. Kerswell, H. Koch, A.W. Lanati, G. ter Maat, N. Martínez-Villegas, L. Nana Yobo, A. Redaa, W. Schäfer, M.R. Swing, R.J.M. Taylor, M.K. Traun, J. Whelan, T. Zhou

S1. Goldschmidt 2022 Workshop

The workshop [“Earth Science meets Data Science: what are our needs for geochemical data, services and analytical capabilities in the 21st century?”](#) was held at the Goldschmidt Conference 2022 (hybrid format). The goals of this workshop were to:

1. Explore scientific challenges in geochemistry;
2. Showcase examples of existing data solutions/infrastructures/services; and
3. Discuss recommendations, best practices and essential features of a globally standardised geochemical data framework;

The primary focus of the workshop lay on exploring the data and infrastructure requirements for addressing future scientific challenges through keynote seminars, breakout working groups, panel and open discussions. In addition, two dedicated tutorials demonstrated the features and capabilities of the EarthChem, GEOROC (DIGIS) and AusGeochem (AuScope Geochemistry Network) data systems, inviting feedback from participants.

Contribution to this workshop gave participants the opportunity to voice their needs directly to the platform and repository creators/managers. Participants benefited from discussions around data transparency, best practices, big data synthesis and inter-laboratory analytical comparisons, actively contributing to bring about a cultural change in the geochemistry community. All workshop organisers and participants have been invited to contribute to this paper (see [Section S1.3](#) for a detailed list of contributors and their roles).

S1.1 Workshop Programme

Day 0 (8 July, 6:00-10:00 HADT): EarthChem & GEOROC tutorial	
06:00-06:15	Welcome & Introductions
06:15-06:45	Overview of Systems
06:45-08:15	Accessing Data
08:15-08:45	Coffee Break
08:45-09:00	Sample Management & Identification
09:00-10:00	Publishing Data
Day 1 (9 July, 10:00-17:00 HADT): Main Workshop	
10:00-10:15	Welcome & Introductions
10:15-11:00	Keynote 1: Sarah Lambart (slides)
11:00-11:15	Coffee Break
11:15-12:00	Keynote 2: Ian Bruno (slides)
12:00-12:45	Round-the-Table Discussion: expectations for this workshop
12:45-13:45	Lunch Break
13:45-14:45	Break-out Session 1: what are requirements for geochemical data?
14:45-15:15	Introduction to OneGeochemistry and the landscape of existing data resources and standards (Lesley Wyborn, slides)
15:15-15:45	Coffee Break
15:45-16:45	Break-out Session 2: how can we achieve these requirements?
16:45-17:00	Final Words & Way Forward

Day 2 (10 July, 12:00-17:00 HADT): AusGeochem tutorial	
12:00-13:00	Rooftop Lunch (in-person participants)
13:00 - 13:45	Introduction to Day 3 and hosts; What is the AGN, Goals of the AGN and The AusGeochem Platform
13:45 - 14:30	Technical Creation of the Platform
14:30 - 16:45	Exercise 1: AusGeochem Landing Page, Registration and Demonstration
	Exercise 2: Adding and Minting a Sample - Single sample upload to a created package - attach data to that sample - visualize data in map and interrogate data through various drop downs.
	Coffee Break
	Exercise 3: Adding Geochemical Data to Created Sample: Single sample upload to - created package - attach data to that sample - visualize data in map and interrogate data through various drop downs.
16:45 - 17:00	AusGeochem into the Future - Developments/Outlook

S1.2 Participating Data Systems

EarthChem is a disciplinary data facility established in 2003 that curates and provides open access to geochemical and petrological observations in digital data collections. Between 2010 and 2020, EarthChem has operated as part of the Interdisciplinary Earth Data Alliance (IEDA), and since 2022 within the reimagined IEDA2, both supported by the US National Science Foundation. EarthChem provides data stewardship services for a broad community of Earth and environmental scientists, including data publishing through the trusted repository service of the EarthChem Library, and data access and mining through synthesis databases (PetDB, EarthChem Portal, Library of Experimental Phase Relations, and the Decade Volcano Portal). EarthChem also established best practices for geochemical and sample-based data through the Editors Roundtable (Goldstein et al. 2014), which led to the Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth & Space Sciences COPDESS (Hanson et al. 2015, Lehnert & Hsu 2015) that continues to advance best practices for data in scholarly publications and provided the foundation for the AGU project “Enabling FAIR Data” (Stall et al. 2017). EarthChem applications and data holdings can be accessed at <https://earthchem.org>.

The **GEOROC** (*Geochemistry of Rocks of the Oceans and Continents*) database contains published geochemical analyses of whole rocks, glasses, minerals and inclusions from eleven different geological settings across the world. It was set up by the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry, Mainz, Germany, and has been available online since the end of 1999. The database provides free access to >32 million individual values of major and trace element concentrations, radiogenic and nonradiogenic isotope ratios as well as analytical ages, compiled from >20,600 published scientific articles. In addition to the chemical analyses, extensive metadata describing the publication, sample and analytical method are stored. Together with PetDB and EarthChem, GEOROC developed a data and metadata schema for geochemical analyses (Lehnert et al., 2000). GEOROC is a key data contributor to the EarthChem Portal, hosted by IEDA2. Since 2021, GEOROC also provides a domain data repository that enables data submissions by the community. The GEOROC database is currently maintained by the Digital Geochemical Data Infrastructure ([DIGIS](#)) initiative at the University of Göttingen. It can be accessed at <https://georoc.eu>.

The **AusGeochem** platform was developed by the AuScope Geochemistry Network (AGN) and collaborator Lithodat to facilitate better organisation, coordination and ability to share data produced by Australian geochemistry laboratories. It differs from EarthChem and GEOROC in that it focuses on collecting data directly from the laboratories, although users can upload existing datasets. The AGN is funded by AuScope, Australia’s provider of infrastructure to the Earth and Geospatial Sciences in Australia, aiming to create wide and open access to earth and geospatial science infrastructure to drive research across government, institutions and industry. AuScope is funded by the Australian Government under the National Collaborative Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). As more and more data are produced in laboratories each day, the amount of data that becomes available for the scientific community through publications represents only the tip of the iceberg, with an appreciable amount of data abandoned on USB or hard disk drives. Therefore, the AGN aimed to build a platform that caters to laboratories, laboratory users and technical staff to make it easier to upload data directly from the instrument into a relational publicly accessible

database. When users upload sample metadata to AusGeochem, laboratory staff performing the analyses can upload the finished data directly into the platform, simultaneously linking the analyses to the sample metadata. With the ability to give samples unique codes and labels through an IGSN minting service, perform statistical analyses, novel capabilities to visualise and synthesise data within the context of large volumes of laboratory generated publicly funded geochemical data, the database simultaneously performs the function of repository and acts as a place for collaboration, interrogation and dissemination of high value geochemistry datasets. The platform links the private, collaborative and public domains. The AusGeochem platform can be accessed at <https://ausgeochem.auscope.org.au>.

S1.3 Workshop Contributors

Name	Affiliation	Workshop Role	Interest in this topic
Marthe Klöcking	Göttingen University; GEOROC	Organiser	
Kerstin Lehnert	Columbia University; IEDA2, EarthChem	Organiser	
Alexander Prent	Curtin University, AusGeochem	Organiser	
Lucia Profeta	Columbia University; IEDA2, EarthChem	Organiser	
Bryant Ware	Curtin University, AusGeochem	Organiser	
Fabian Kohlmann	Lithodat, AusGeochem	Tutorial organiser	
Wayne Noble	Lithodat, AusGeochem	Tutorial organiser	
Lesley Wyborn	Australian National University	Organiser; invited keynote speaker	Where to start on developing machine-actionable standards and vocabularies for geochemical data
Ian Bruno	CCDC	Participant; invited keynote speaker	To share experiences from chemistry and crystallography and learn about common challenges
Sarah Lambart	University of Utah	Participant; invited keynote speaker	Know how I can become a contributor - learn about new developments
Halimulati Ananuer	Macquarie University	Participant	Geochemical database and management
Michael Badawi	University of Lorraine	Participant	
Nicholas Barber	University of Cambridge	Participant	Interested in statistical treatments of large geochemical datasets
Harry Becker	Freie Universität Berlin	Participant	Metadata in data repositories

Maurice Brodbeck	Trinity College Dublin	Participant	What is good geochemical data? Reporting standards. Access and use of platforms.
Hang Deng	Peking University	Participant	Learn more about open access geochemical database
Kai Deng	ETH Zurich	Participant	Geochemical data compilation and reuse
Gabriel Franco	University of South Carolina	Participant	Getting and insider's perspective on the main geochemistry databases
Yajie Gao	Australian National University	Participant	Learn more about open database
Khalid Mohammed Ghasera	Aligarh Muslim University	Participant	Big data resources
Jingyi Huang	Johns Hopkins University	Participant	learn about how this data system works and how data managed
Buchanan Kerswell	Miami University	Participant	Student research
Jieun Kim	Northwestern University	Participant	Available geochemical databases
Hilde Koch	University College Dublin	Participant	Reliability of Geochemical Data of Database. Is it possible to get access to raw data? How can you make existing databases more visible?
Anthony Lanati	University Münster and Macquarie University	Participant	Ethical use of the databases, as well as contributing data and ensuring my data is FAIR
Nadia Martínez-Villegas	IPICYT	Participant	Learn about opendatabase and how to better report and manage data
Nicolas Randazzo	McMaster University	Participant	Interested in Big Data and wanted to learn more about data repositories
Ahmad Redaa	King Abdulaziz University	Participant	Learn about open access sources of geological datasets

Wiebke Schäfer	Friedrich-Alexander University	Participant	How to make my data accessible and pros and cons of making data accessible to everyone
Megan Swing	University of Toronto/ Royal Ontario Museum	Participant	Learning more about the the types of databases other researchers use
Marie Katrine Traun	University of Copenhagen	Participant	Integrating better data practices in data collection and laboratories and exploring the potential of big data geochemical studies with advanced statistics
Jo Whelan	Northern Territory Geological Survey	Participant	Learn about the data models, vocabularies and standards that are being applied with a view to ensure that the Survey is taking a consistent approach with data
Lucien Nana Yobo	Texas A&M University	Participant	Learn about the various geochemical database
Tengfei Zhou	China University of Petroleum (East China)	Participant	Big data and Geochemical data

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